

PREDICTIONS OF CRACK ARREST UNDER CYCLIC LOADING IN CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A model to predict crack arrest from an initial unbridged defect in fibre reinforced titanium metal matrix composites subjected to cyclic loading has been developed. Its basis is that crack arrest occurs if relatively few bridging fibres fail in the crack wake as they are breached by matrix fatigue crack growth, and experimentally the onset of fibre failure can be correlated with the nominal maximum stress intensity factor, K_{max} , applied over the fatigue cycle. The model has been used to predict the influence of crack size and shape on crack arrest. Great care is required if predictions of crack arrest validated for through-thickness cracks are to be extended to part through-thickness defects.

Keywords: metal matrix composites, fatigue crack growth resistance curves, unbridged crack, fibre bridging, crack arrest

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently continuous fibre reinforced titanium metal matrix composites (MMC's) are being considered as structural materials for elevated temperature applications in aerospace where weight saving is an important factor. Many experimental studies have shown that localised dominant cracks are observed in such composites⁽¹⁻⁶⁾. This has enabled the crack growth behaviour to be characterised in terms of an effective stress intensity range and such concepts could prove useful in establishing their "fitness for purpose".

However, it is clear that there will be no unique relationship between the nominal applied stress intensity range and the crack growth resistance of the composite, which is independent of testpiece geometry and fibre architecture. Indeed factors such as the number of fibres bridging the crack wake, the interfacial strength, and the initial unbridged crack size and shape have all been shown to be important. Many numerical and analytical models have also been developed to predict the influence of such variables and good progress has been made⁽⁷⁻¹²⁾. Moreover, recent work has shown that if no fibre fracture occurs then crack arrest (where $da/dN \leq 10^{-8}$ mm/cycle) normally results in such materials⁽⁶⁾. One useful concept could then be to establish the criteria under which crack arrest can be predicted as a function of crack shape and initial (unbridged) crack depth. In essence this must address the conditions under which the first fibres to be breached by the fatigue crack will not fail.

In this context the importance of bridging scale length also must be appreciated⁽⁹⁾. Indeed, great care is required if results from a specific initial unbridged crack depth are to be extrapolated to a different unbridged crack depth⁽⁶⁾. The primary purpose of this paper then is to consider the conditions under which crack arrest can be predicted in such composites based on the use of fracture mechanics parameters.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The material was supplied by BP Metal Composites Ltd in the form of a fully consolidated six-ply plate of 1mm thickness, with a Ti-6Al-4V alloy matrix reinforced unidirectionally with continuous Sigma (SM1240) silicon carbide fibres to a fibre volume fraction of nominally 31%. These fibres are coated with dual carbon and titanium boride layers and are of diameter of approximately 100 μ m. Specimens of nominal dimensions (4.5x1x72mm³) were machined from the plate by Electro Discharge Machining (EDM).

All tests were performed on single edge notched specimens. A through-thickness notch of depth 1.1mm was cut in each specimen with a 180 μ m thickness diamond blade. The notch depth was measured using a travelling microscope, and gives an initial unbridged crack length to width ratio, a_0/W , approximately equal to 0.25.

Cracks were grown by fatigue perpendicular to the direction of the fibre reinforcement and parallel to the stacking direction of the fibres within a mat. Tests were carried out in three point bending using an overall span to width ratio, s/W , equal to 13.3.

ESH servo-hydraulic testing machines fitted with 1 and 10kN load cells were used at frequencies of 0.5 and 10Hz respectively (note that this former facility is limited to frequencies ≤ 0.5 Hz due to the rate of working of its small air cooled hydraulic power pack). A constant load range, ΔP , was maintained during each test. This allows the nominal stress intensity range, ΔK_{app} , to increase with crack length. Changes in crack length were monitored using a direct current potential difference technique and crack growth rates were calculated using the seven point secant method⁽¹¹⁾. Note that care must be taken when using this method of crack growth monitoring to ensure that calibration curves relating changes in normalised potential V/V_0 (where V_0 is the reference potential at a_0/W) to changes in normalised crack length (a/W), are appropriate to the specimen size under consideration. Such modelling experiments have been conducted and are considered in detail elsewhere⁽⁵⁾.

Effects of stress ratio, where $R=(\sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max})$ and σ_{min} , σ_{max} are the minimum and maximum stresses applied over the fatigue cycles respectively, on crack growth rates, da/dN , have been considered. Stress ratios of $R=0.1$ and 0.5 and frequencies of 0.5 and 10 Hz were used respectively. Different load ranges were employed to give different initial ΔK_{app} values. All fatigue tests were carried out at ambient temperature.

Polished metallographic sections were studied optically to reveal fatigue crack paths and the incidence of fibre failure. Fatigue fracture surfaces were examined using an Hitachi S 4000 Field Emission Gun Scanning Electron Microscope operating at 20kV and 45° tilt.

3. RESULTS

In all tests to date localised dominant cracks have been produced under fatigue loading. Optical micrographs of interrupted tests show such cracks clearly, Figure 1. In this particular composite system they often grow off-axis and this feature is considered elsewhere⁽⁴⁾. Here, Figure 1 illustrates the mechanism of fatigue crack growth where intact fibres bridge the growing fatigue crack in its wake. A representative fractograph after catastrophic failure is shown in Figure 2. Relatively long pull-out lengths of between 130-200 μ m are observed. Such observations are consistent with the *failure of fibres within the crack wake but behind the growing crack tip* (other support for this concept is given elsewhere⁽⁶⁾). Thus an important characteristic of studies to date, is that during stable fatigue crack growth, fibres fail only behind the growing crack-tip (ahead of this crack-tip they do, of course, debond) i.e. fibres are breached by the fatigue crack *before* they fail.

The dependence of crack growth rate, da/dN , on the nominal applied stress intensity range, ΔK_{app} , is shown in Figure 3, for a stress ratio, $R=0.5$, and for four different load ranges, ΔP , of 43, 53, 60 and 67N. These correspond to initial ΔK_{app} values of 12, 14, 16 and 18MPa \sqrt{m} respectively. Note that although dominant cracks grow off-axis at the lower load ranges of 53 and 60N, the absolute length of crack deflection away from the line of maximum bending moment is extremely small compared with

the large span employed. Of note from Figure 3 is that composite failure occurs under the three higher initial ΔK_{app} values (that is 14, 16 and 18MPa \sqrt{m}), compared with crack arrest occurring at the lower initial ΔK_{app} level of 12MPa \sqrt{m} .

Figure 4 shows the dependence of da/dN on ΔK_{app} at the lower stress ratio, $R=0.1$. Again four different load ranges, ΔP , of 67, 82, 92 and 107N are illustrated. These correspond to initial ΔK_{app} values of 18, 22, 25 and 28MPa \sqrt{m} respectively. Catastrophic composite failure occurs only at the higher initial ΔK_{app} values of 25 and 28MPa \sqrt{m} , while crack arrest occurs at the lower initial ΔK_{app} levels of 22 and 18MPa \sqrt{m} . Little effect of cyclic frequency has been observed generally at ambient temperature⁽⁴⁾, and therefore even for the tests performed at the different frequencies of 10Hz and 0.5Hz useful comparisons of crack growth rates as a function of stress ratio can still be made.

It is now of interest to examine conditions under which crack arrest can be promoted. A deduction made in the present work is that crack arrest occurs only if relatively few or no fibres fail during crack growth for the unbridged cut notch (this assertion has been validated in other systems where fibre fracture has been monitored using acoustic emission, but strictly in the present work it is a deduction made from the form of the crack growth resistance curves shown in Figures 3 and 4). In earlier work⁽³⁾ on a similar testpiece geometry it was suggested that the integrity of the first two rows of fibres as they were breached by the fatigue crack could be critical, and indeed as the number of intact bridging fibres increases then the composite becomes increasingly damage tolerant even though the matrix crack length increases⁽⁶⁾.

A simple comparison of the conditions for crack arrest for the two levels of mean stress, $R=0.1$ and 0.5, considered here suggests strongly the influence of the value of applied K_{max} , see Table 1. In view of the above comments, and the observed mechanism of crack growth, Figure 1, it is clear that the value of applied K_{max} after the first row of fibres has been breached may be important and this is also shown in Table 1. For this particular testpiece geometry it may therefore be inferred that the value of K_{max} after the first row of fibres is a valid parameter with which to characterise fibre failure: if K_{max} is less than 27.5MPa \sqrt{m} then crack arrest is observed. The observations are of course specific to the fibre composite architecture under consideration, but it is useful to consider if this approach can be extended to predict crack arrest for a range of crack sizes, crack shapes and testpiece geometries.

For a through-thickness crack, to ensure growth passed the first row of fibres a crack increment of 160 μm has been used and a perfect distribution of fibres has been assumed. With these assumptions, Figures 5 and 6 indicate the predicted level of K_{max} achieved after the first row of fibres for a range of initial ΔK_{app} values and initial unbridged crack depths normalised with respect to the testpiece width, a_0/W , for testpieces subjected to cyclic bending and cyclic tension respectively. In these examples, because the increment of crack depth is relatively small compared with the testpiece width, little difference is predicted for cyclic bending versus tension, see Figures 5 and 6, but a marked influence of initial unbridged crack depth is sometimes observed. Note, that it is unconservative to assume that the crack arrest of a smaller initial unbridged crack can be predicted from crack arrest of a larger initial unbridged crack, *when it is subjected to the same initial stress intensity range*, because the fixed absolute increment of crack depth required to breach the first row of fibres will produce a larger increase in K_{max} for the smaller initial crack depth.

Such predictions of K_{max} after the first row of fibres can also be made for the growth of part-through-thickness cracks, see Figure 7. In this example, the initial defect size and growing crack have both been assumed to be semi-circular, and a range of initial normalised crack depths have been considered. Note that the increment of crack depth must now be calculated on an equivalent area fraction basis to ensure that the same number of bridging fibres are considered when compared with the through-thickness crack (for which the experimental basis of crack arrest has been defined). The levels of maximum peak-stresses applied to produce the initial levels of applied K_{max} (for a crack depth of a_0) are also given in Figure 7.

4. DISCUSSION

The results of the present work appear to define a useful methodology of approach to predicting crack arrest under cyclic loading from an initial unbridged defect. It assumes that crack arrest will occur if significant number of fibres do not fail in the crack wake after they have been breached by the (growing) fatigue crack tip. Fibre failure appears to be controlled by the maximum stress intensity factor applied over the fatigue cycle, but this occurs only behind the (growing) fatigue crack tip. More exactly, fibre fracture must depend upon the precise level of local crack opening displacements that the (intact) fibre resists during the loading sequence, but for geometrically similar testpieces and cracks (i.e. growth past the first row of fibres and for through-thickness cracks) this will be related simply to the nominal maximum stress intensity factor applied over the fatigue cycle. Thus to promote crack arrest, levels of K_{\max} must be kept below a critical value, estimated as $27.5\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ in this present work, Table 1, for crack growth passed the first row of fibres. Crack growth may of course, continue after the first row of fibres since it is a function of the effective stress intensity range, ΔK_{eff} , at the growing crack tip, but even for high initial levels of ΔK_{app} crack growth is eventually predicted to arrest, see Figure 4.

This model of crack growth indicates clearly the care required if specific crack arrest predictions are to be applied to other crack shapes and sizes, see Figures 5, 6 and 7. For through-thickness cracks (on which the experimental basis of the model has been validated) predictions of the influence of initial crack size are relatively straightforward, see Figures 5 and 6. For example, from Figure 5, if a *constant* initial applied stress intensity range of $21.5\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ is applied to cracks of a range of initial depths, only those cracks of depth *greater* than 0.45mm ($a_0/W \geq 0.10$) can be predicted to arrest with certainty. Much experimental work is required to quantify such predictions, but initial results reported elsewhere⁽⁶⁾ are encouraging. Care is thus needed to define the combination of applied stress range and defect size that may be permitted.

The extension of the model to part-through-thickness cracks is more problematic. A simple approach has been adopted to produce Figure 7, but it has not considered fully the stability conditions of the growing crack as it interacts and breaches initially a discrete number of fibres. Since growth is now non-uniform through-thickness a reduced number of fibres will be breached for any given crack growth increment, and thus premature fibre failure may result at lower nominal applied values of K_{\max} (note that the limiting value of K_{\max} calculated after the first row of fibres to prevent fibre failure of $27.5\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ is specific only to one composite row i.e. six fibres bridging the crack). Thus, although the predicted maximum tolerable stresses for such defects, see Figure 7, are of interest detailed experimental verification is necessary and these allowable stresses may be unconservative. Such studies are underway at present, and they include the use of in-situ acoustic emission evaluation to identify fibre fracture during cyclic loading.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A model to predict crack arrest from an initial unbridged defect in fibre reinforced titanium metal matrix composites subjected to cyclic loading has been developed. Fibre fracture has been shown to be controlled primarily by the level of applied maximum stress intensity factor, K_{\max} , during the fatigue cycle, but fibre failure occurs only in the crack wake and behind the growing crack tip. The model has been used to predict the influence of crack shape and size on crack arrest.

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7. REFERENCES

1. Johnson, W.S., *Mechanical Fatigue of Advanced Materials*, Eds Ritchie, R.O. et al, MCE Publications, Santa Barbara, January 1991, pp.357-377.

2. Walls, D., Bao, G. and Zok, F., *Mechanical Fatigue of Advanced Materials*, Eds Ritchie, R.O. et al, MCE Publications, Santa Barbara, January 1991, pp.343-356.
3. Bowen, P., Ibbotson, A.R. and Beevers, C.J., *Mechanical Fatigue of Advanced Materials*, Eds Ritchie, R.O. et al, MCE Publications, Santa Barbara, January 1991, pp.379-394.
4. Barney, C., Beevers, C.J. and Bowen, P., *J. Composites*, Vol. 24, No. 3, pp.229-234, January 1993.
5. Bowen, P., Cotterill, P.J. and Ibbotson, A.R., *Test Techniques for Metal Matrix Composites*, Ed. Goddard, N.D.R., IOPP, London, 1990, pp.82-96.
6. Bowen, P., *The Processing, Properties and Applications of Metallic and Ceramic Materials*, Eds Loretto, M.H. and Beevers, C.J., MCE Publications, Birmingham, September 1992, pp. 697-718.
7. Marshall, D.B., Cox, B.N. and Evans, A.G., *Acta Metall*, Vol. 33, pp. 2013-2021, 1985.
8. Budiansky, B., Hutchinson, J.W. and Evans, A.G., *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 34, pp.167-189, 1986.
9. Cox, B.N. and Lo, C.S., *Acta Metall et Materialia*, Vol. 40, pp.69-80, 1992.
10. McMeeking, R.M. and Evans, A.G., *Mechanics of Materials*, Vol. 9, pp. 217-227, 1990.
11. Cardona, D.C., Barney, C. and Bowen, P., *J. Composites*, Vol. 24, pp.122-128, January 1993.
12. Cardona, D.C. and Bowen, P., *Theoretical Concepts and Numerical Analysis of Fatigue*, MCE Publications, Birmingham, May 1992.

Table 1 Summary of initial ΔK_{app} , K_{max} after first row of fibres, mean stress and test outcome

Stress Ratio	Initial ΔK (MPa \sqrt{m})	Initial K_{max} (MPa \sqrt{m})	K_{max} after 1st row fibres (MPa \sqrt{m})	Test Result
0.5	12.1	24.2	25.8	Crack Arrest Catastrophic Failure
0.5	13.8	27.6	29.8	
0.1	22.3	24.8	27.5	Crack Arrest Catastrophic Failure
0.1	25.0	27.8	30.2	

Figure 1 Metallographic sections (a) $R=0.5$, $\nu=10\text{Hz}$, initial $\Delta K_{app}=12.0\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, after crack arrest, (b) $R=0.1$, $\nu=0.5\text{Hz}$, initial $\Delta K_{app}=22.3\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, after crack arrest

Figure 2 Fatigue fractograph after failure, initial $\Delta K_{app}=18\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, $R=0.5$ and $\nu=10\text{Hz}$

Figure 3 da/dN versus ΔK for $R=0.5$, $\nu=10\text{Hz}$

Figure 4 da/dN versus ΔK for $R=0.1$, $\nu=0.5\text{Hz}$

Figure 5 Predictions of crack arrest as a function of a_0/W , $R=0.1$, bending, through-thickness cracks

Figure 6 Predictions of crack arrest as a function of a_0/W , $R=0.1$, tension, through-thickness cracks

Figure 7 Predictions of crack arrest as a function of a_0/W , $R=0.1$, tension, for semi-circular cracks. K_{max} values are shown at surface positions. Initial applied nominal maximum stress, σ_{max} , values are given in brackets.